

This preprint has not undergone peer review (when applicable) or any post-submission improvements or corrections. The Version of Record of this contribution is published in In International Conference on Human-Computer Interaction (pp. 47-65). Cham: Springer Nature Switzerland, and is available online at https://doi.org/10.1007/978-3-031-34917-1_4.

Visual Ambient Assisted Living technologies for different daily activities: Users' requirements and data handling preferences

Julia Offermann¹[0000-0003-1870-2775], Caterina Maidhof¹[0000-0002-0573-4498],
and Martina Ziefle¹[0000-0002-6105-4729]

Chair of Communication Science, RWTH Aachen University, Aachen, Germany
offermann,maidhof,ziefle@comm.rwth-aachen.de

Abstract. Ambient Assisted Living technologies (AAL) represent an opportunity to meet the high demands of support in care due to demographic change and enable older people to live autonomously and as long as possible in their own home environments. Despite their potential, AAL technologies and in particular visual-based systems have hardly been used neither in home care nor professional care due to a lack of user acceptance. Therefore, the present study investigates future users' privacy and data handling needs contrasting the usage of video-based AAL technologies (VAAL) for three different types of daily activities: household, social, and intimate activities. Applying an online survey, a sample of N=122 participants took part and evaluated three contrasting activities in which VAAL technologies were used by assessing different conditions of technology usage, different entities getting access to recorded data, different storage options as well as different storage durations. The results showed some significant differences regarding the evaluation of the conditions of using VAAL technologies and the entities being allowed to have access to recorded data differentiating between the three activity types. In contrast, storage options and storage durations were not evaluated differently. Overall, the results indicate a rather generic attitude towards VAAL technologies being only slightly affected by different activity types. Beyond that, the results showed that privacy and data handling preferences are closely related to the perception and acceptance of VAAL technology. These insights enable to derive recommendations and information strategies to enable a targeted and user-centered technology development.

Keywords: Video-based AAL technology · data handling · privacy · technology acceptance · user preferences · quantitative study

1 Introduction

To meet the growing challenges of demographic change, innovative approaches such as Ambient Assisted Living (AAL) technologies have been developed to

support and care for the elderly and those in need of long-term care [1–3]. Besides sensor- and audio-based technologies, video-based devices, e.g., RGB cameras, RGB-D devices, or thermal cameras have been increasingly used in recent years enabling continuous monitoring of events and environments and providing detailed visual information [4, 5]. Advances in computer vision and underlying algorithms have paved the way for the development of intelligent visual systems being used in various fields, but being particularly promising in the field of health care [4–7]. Such systems are not only capable of transmitting video in real-time but are also able to extract useful and relevant information from the visual data and make this information available to specific target groups. Typical examples of applications of visual technologies in health care are predominantly the detection and prevention of emergencies such as falls, but also physiological monitoring, detection of activities of daily living, or analyses of gait, human behavior and corresponding changes [4, 8, 9].

Although such visual AAL approaches (short: VAAL) have a great potential to support people in their daily lives by increasing their safety and independence in older age, there are also barriers and concerns, especially regarding privacy and data security violations, being able to impact the acceptance and adoption of such technical innovations [10–12]. In more detail, concerns about data security and resulting feelings of an invasion of the own privacy play a more relevant role within the assessments of cameras and VAAL technologies compared to non-visual approaches, such as audio- or sensor-based systems [13, 14]. Beyond this knowledge, a detailed understanding of users’ specific preferences regarding privacy and data handling and their role in the perception and acceptance of VAAL technologies is so far missing. However, identified preferences and relationships between privacy requirements, data handling preferences, and the acceptance of VAAL technology enable to derive concrete recommendations for more targeted and user-centred technology development.

Therefore, this study aimed at an investigation of privacy and data handling preferences related to the usage of VAAL technologies for different activities of daily living. Thereby, three different exemplary types of activities were focused on in order to analyze whether the context of using VAAL technologies influenced the preferences with regard to privacy and data handling. Beyond that, it was of interest to identify whether privacy and data handling preferences played a relevant role in the perception and acceptance of VAAL technologies. In the following, the research state regarding VAAL technologies, technology acceptance, and the role of perceptions related to privacy and data handling is summarized. Subsequently, the empirical approach of the study is introduced, describing the concept, the structure of the online survey, methods of data analysis as well as the characteristics of the sample. Then, the results of the study are presented. Finally, we discuss the insights, derive implications and recommendations, and outline limitations as well as ideas for future research.

1.1 VAAL technologies

Despite their diversity in functions and design, all AAL technologies have a common aim in terms of providing support and assistance in older age. In this regard, literature reviews (e.g., by Rashidi and Mihailidis [1] or Blackman et al. [2]) provide an overview of relevant approaches, functions, and application areas, e.g., detection of emergencies, reminding functions, or relief in everyday life.

Addressing not only older people in need of care themselves but also their (in)formal caregivers, the application of AAL technologies has the potential to enable a longer and more autonomous life within their own home environments and to provide support by analyzing health-related data [1, 2]. In this context, the shape and design of the technical applications are extremely diverse, ranging from small, wearable sensors to systems that are installed in the environment and integrate different types of sensors. In addition, the application contexts are quite diverse, aiming at support and assistance in private environments and professional care settings, such as hospitals, rehabilitation and specific care facilities, or nursing homes. Thereby, the functional spectrum of the systems and technologies is also very broad: more generic functions aim at the detection of individual activities and movements for health monitoring [17], of social activities [15], or health parameters to motivate physical activity [16], while specific functions address the identification of symptoms of dementia, e.g., detect and analyze typical and changes in patterns of movements and behaviors [18] or providing early notification of physicians and caregivers based on the detection of falls and specific dangerous situations (e.g., [19, 20]).

Aiming at support and assistance in older age at home, the integration of video-based applications within the own home environments has been focused in different research areas [4, 21]. Such approaches enable the extraction of useful information from the video data based on intelligent systems and underlying algorithms [6, 5] enabling the previously described functions, e.g., detailed analyses of gait patterns or human behavior as well as the detection of emergencies, falls, and other dangerous situations. Thanks to visual capturing by one or just a few sensors information-rich data output can be obtained and can be easily interpreted by humans [4]. This makes video-based technology (VAAL) a highly effective and efficient health-monitoring technology given also the decreasing prices for camera sensors and constant improvements in computer vision [4].

In summary, a large number of applications are aimed at supporting and assisting people in their private home environment based on intelligent monitoring and analysis using computer vision. Beyond the potential and the advantages of these applications, future users' acceptance and willingness to use them are necessary.

1.2 Technology Perception and Acceptance

In the last decades, technology acceptance has frequently been analyzed by applying well-established models, namely, the Technology Acceptance Model [22] and the Unified Theory of Acceptance and Use of Technology [23], as well as

their extensions and adaptations [24]. These models provided the basis for numerous studies and enabled an understanding of acceptance patterns and processes for new technologies. In addition to model-related parameters such as perceived usefulness and ease of use, research has shown that individual user characteristics (e.g., age, gender, experience) play a decisive role indicating that technology acceptance differs among different user groups (e.g., [23]). Besides the user as an acceptance subject, acceptance also differs depending on the specific type of technology (acceptance object) and the respective application context. Therefore, the perception and acceptance of a specific technology have to be examined separately taking specific technology- and context-dependent parameters into account.

In this regard, previous research has shown that context-related perceptions of benefits and concerns play a decisive role in its acceptance and sustainable adoption [10, 25]. Enabling an autonomous life, support within the activities of daily living, relief for caring relatives, and increased safety represent major motives to use and advantages of using AAL technologies [10, 25, 12]. On the opposite, concerns regarding data security, a lack of human interaction, loneliness, and predominantly concerns regarding the intrusion of one’s own privacy (i.e., perceived surveillance, unauthorized access to sensible health data) represent the most relevant barriers associated with the usage of AAL technologies [10, 12, 26]. The latter is becoming of utmost importance for the specific case of VAAL technologies such as cameras: here, previous research identified a comparably low acceptance and reluctant willingness to use camera-based AAL technologies to capture health-related data within the own home environment indicating high assessments of privacy concerns (e.g., [14, 27]).

Due to its meaning for the acceptance of VAAL technologies, the multifaceted phenomenon of privacy is addressed in more detail in the following.

1.3 Privacy and Data Handling

Understanding privacy as a state of mind or an assertion of control (e.g., [28]), there are different approaches to describe and differentiate between diverse facets and dimensions of privacy (e.g., [28–30]). For instance, Burgoon [30] distinguishes four dimensions of privacy (informational, social, psychological, and physical privacy) and highlights the ability to control the specific aspects of privacy within the dimensions as relevant for the perception of whether privacy is high or low. Furthermore, privacy is defined as a regulation process that depends on personal and situational factors and is, therefore, contextual [31, 32]. Focusing on digital environments and technologies, the regulation process is even more challenging, as it easily leads to perceptions of loss of control over personal information and people focus more on protecting against privacy threats than on meeting their actual needs [33] which among other, are contemplation, autonomy and confiding [45, 34]. In this regard, digital (health) technologies enabling ubiquitous surveillance, storing of high amounts of data, and allowing rapid and global dissemination of information represent major threats to privacy [32].

Considering VAAL technologies, privacy is predominantly focused as a concern in terms of fears of access and misuse of personal information and feelings of permanent surveillance, having the potential to decrease acceptance and finally hinder the adoption of such systems [10, 11, 35]. While the digital environment and especially the specific visual technology are responsible for major privacy threats and concerns, these perceived dangers may be partly diminished by technological features itself such as image filters [4], limited timeslots for monitoring [36] or the restriction of data access and storage duration [37, 38]. Indeed, especially when visual-based technologies are applied and with the definitions of privacy mentioned above in mind, privacy can be understood to be multi-faceted and context-dependent. Regarding aspects of context, previous research identified the performed activity as a relevant impacting factor for the comfortableness of being monitored with a camera-based technology [39] indicating that sensitive activities (e.g., hygiene care) were perceived as most uncomfortable. Of course, performed activities depend on situational factors which may play an important role in privacy perception. In this regard, findings showed that the acceptance of medical camera monitoring declines the more private the monitored spaces are [40] and the more skin is shown [41]. Taking personal factors into account, previous research showed that perceptions of safety and security [42] as well as the need for care [43] and the degree of disability [44] may impact the acceptance of VAAL technology. To sum up, these insights show that privacy is malleable and - under certain situational and personal circumstances - can be governed by a trade-off with various benefits associated with visual monitoring, e.g., increased security and helpfulness [43, 42].

Beyond the insights of previous research, it is so far not well known which technical requirements are relevant and which ways of data handling are preferred (data access and data storage) focusing on the usage of VAAL technologies being applied for different activities of daily living.

2 Methods

Within this section, the methodological approach of the study is described, starting with the research aim and the underlying empirical concept. Subsequently, the structure of the online survey, the data analysis, and the characteristics of the sample are described.

2.1 Empirical Concept

The present study aimed at a detailed investigation of future users' preferences regarding technological requirements, different ways of data access, and different options of data storage within the context of applying VAAL technologies for different activities of daily living. For that purpose and based on a literature review and a preceding qualitative study, relevant parameters regarding technological requirements, data access, and data storage were selected.

Enabling a comparison of diverse activities of daily living, three different activity types were selected covering a broad range of possible activities: 1) household activity, 2) social activity, and 3) intimate activity. For each of the three activity types, a short scenario was presented to the participants in randomized order to control for order effects. For the scenario of a household activity, it was described that during cooking, cleaning, and tidying up a fire was caused as detected by the monitoring camera. The scenario of a social activity focused on longer interactions (i.e., playing and chatting) with friends or (grand)children and described that forgotten medicine was detected by the video-based system due to deviations from normal behavior. The last scenario described an intimate activity in terms of showering and changing clothes during which a fall was happening (due to physical decline in older age) and was also detected by the video-based AAL system. Following each scenario, the participants assessed their preferred ways of data access and data storage as well as technical requirements and technology acceptance.

The empirical concept was designed to answer the following research questions related to the usage of VAAL technologies:

1. RQ1: What are the most and least important aspects of technical requirements, data access, and data storage?
2. RQ2: To what extent does the activity type affect the evaluation of technical requirements, data access, and data storage?
3. RQ3: Which privacy and data handling preferences (requirements, access, storage) are relevant for the acceptance of VAAL technology?

2.2 Online Survey

An online survey was conceptualized and consisted of two main parts. Within the first part, the participants were asked for demographic information, such as their age, gender, educational level, and living situation. Following that, the participants indicated health-related information by stating if they suffer from a chronic illness and if they needed assistance and care in their everyday life (answer options: yes/no). In addition, they indicated if they had previous experiences in caring for other persons, i.e. professional and private care experience (answer options: yes/no). Addressing attitudinal factors, the participants' technical understanding, psychometrics, and their general attitude towards privacy were assessed.

At the beginning of the second part of the survey, the participants were introduced to VAAL technologies. The participants were then asked to evaluate three different types of activities of daily living imagining themselves living with a VAAL system being installed in their home environment. Three specific activities (see section 2.1) of daily living were described within scenarios in a randomized order. For each scenario, the participants assessed different technical requirements (6 items), different ways of data handling (6 items), and two different options for data storage. All items are illustrated in Figure 1. Storage duration was evaluated by selecting the preferred option out of 5 options: not

stored at all, max. 1 week, max. 1 month, max. 1 year, unlimited (see Figure 3). Furthermore, the participants evaluated their acceptance, perceived benefits, and perceived barriers of using the visual-based AAL system for the respective type of activity. If not described otherwise, all items were rated on six-point Likert scales (1 = I completely disagree, 6 = I completely agree).

At the end of the survey, the participants could write their comments, feedback, and critiques regarding the survey or the topic in an open field.

2.3 Data Analysis

We report descriptive statistics for the evaluations indicating means (M) and standard deviations (SD). To investigate potential differences between the three activity types one-way repeated measure ANOVAs were applied. To examine potential relationships between the analysed constructs, correlation analyses were performed. Spearman's ρ was used for bivariate correlations and Pillai's V was stated for the omnibus test of ANOVAs. Linear regression analyses were calculated to analyze the relevance of the data handling preferences for technology acceptance. The level of statistical significance (p) was set at 5%.

2.4 Participants

N=122 participants completed the online survey, and passed the data cleaning procedure (i.e., control for speeders, quality fails etc.) and their data sets were used for further statistical analyses. The participants were on average 38.39 years old (SD=16.69; min=17; max=81) and almost two-thirds of the participants were female (63.9%, n=78). The educational level of the sample was comparably high with the majority (61.5%, n=75) holding a university degree, 3.3% (n=4) a PhD, and 29.5% (n=36) an university entrance qualification. Only 5.7% (n=7) indicated lower educational levels.

Asked for their health status, almost a quarter of the participants indicated suffering from a chronic illness (24.6%, n=30) and only 6.6% (n=8) reported being in need of assistance and care. Beyond that, 13.1% (n=16) reported having professional experience in care, while more than a third of the participants (36.9%, n=45) reported having private experience in care by indicating that they have already cared for a person in need of care in their personal environment.

3 Results

In this section, the results of the empirical study are described, starting with an overview of the assessments of technical requirements and data handling preferences overall. In the second step, the results are shown differentiated between the three activity types. In the last step, relationships between technical requirements, data handling preferences, and technology acceptance are communicated.

3.1 Evaluation of Requirements and Data Handling (RQ1)

The descriptive overall results (independent from the three activity types) of the evaluated technical requirements and data handling preferences are visualized in Figure 1. Starting with the **technical requirements**, it was evaluated as most important that *Technology must be controllable and checkable at all times* (M=5.01; SD=.88). *Technology must be able to be switched on and off at any time* (M=4.82; SD=.92) received the second highest agreement. Further, the participants slightly agreed with the requirement that *Technology must only be used when alone* (M=3.96; SD=1.17). Referring to specific requirements regarding what is allowed to be recorded, the participants showed indistinct evaluations. They slightly agreed with the requirement that *No video recordings are allowed* (M=3.70; SD=1.15) and they showed neutral evaluations of the statement that *Technology may record all activities* (M=3.48; SD=1.21). However, the requirement that *Only audio recordings are allowed to be made* was in tendency slightly rejected (M=3.35; SD=1.12).

Fig. 1. Descriptive results of data handling preferences.

Asked for different entities being allowed to **access the recorded data**, the participants showed very distinct evaluation patterns. Data access was most desired for the respective persons themselves: *Myself* (M=5.35; SD=.88). *Medical personnel* (M=4.81; SD=.90) and *Family members* (M=4.69; SD=1.03) were also

clearly allowed to have access to the recorded data. For *Police and fire departments* (M=4.20; SD=1.08), the results showed a lower, but still clear agreement for data access. In contrast, data access was unequivocally rejected for *Health Insurances* (M=2.50; SD=1.27) and *Companies* (M=2.40; SD=1.33).

Considering the **storage options**, it was clearly preferred that *Data may be stored locally at my own home only* (M=4.69; SD=1.04), while the option that *Data may be stored in a cloud or at the manufacturer* was rather rejected (M=3.05; SD=1.38).

The results of the evaluation of **storage duration** options showed that overall 21.30% (n=26) of the participants selected the option that *Data may be stored unlimitedly*. Further, 25.4% (n=31) preferred that *Data may be stored for max. 1 week.*, while 23.8% (n=29) of the participants desired the option *Data may be stored for max. 1 month.* Finally, 29.5% (n=36) selected the option *Data may be stored for max. 1 year.* The option that *Data may not be stored at all* was not selected averaged over all three activity types. However, differences dependent on the three activity types are described in the next subsection.

3.2 Preferences for Different Activities (RQ2)

The descriptive results of the evaluated data handling preferences depending on the three activity types are visualized in Figure 2. The results of one-way repeated measure analyses revealed overall rather similar evaluation patterns with significant differences only in single aspects.

Starting with the **technical requirements**, the most relevant requirements that technology must be *able to be switched on and off at any time* (F(2,118)=2.67; p=.07, n.s.), *controllable and checkable at all times* (F(2,117)=.31; p=.74, n.s.), and *only be used when alone* (F(2,117)=1.51; p=.23, n.s.) were all not evaluated significantly differently. Further, also the requirement that *Technology may record all activities* (F(2,118)=2.11; p=.13, n.s.) did not reveal significant differences for the three activity types. Instead, the last two requirements were evaluated significantly differently indicating a higher relevance of these aspects for intimate compared to social and household activities: first, the requirement *No video recordings are allowed* (F(2,117)=3.87; $p < .05$) received the highest agreement for intimate activities (M=3.86; SD=1.44), followed by social (M=3.73; SD=1.44) and lastly household activities (M=3.48; SD=1.44); second, that *Only audio recordings are allowed to be made* (F(2,115)=4.43; $p < .05$) received a slight agreement for intimate activities (M=3.60; SD=1.38), while it was slightly rejected for social (M=3.28; SD=1.29) and household activities (M=3.26; SD=1.35).

Moving to the different options of **data access**, allowing data access for *Myself* (F(2,118)=.16; p=.85, n.s.) and *Medical personnel* (F(2,117)=.17; p=.85, n.s.) were not evaluated significantly different. In line with this, also the both rejected alternatives of providing data access for *Health insurances* (F(2,115)=2.11; p=.11, n.s.) and *Companies* (F(2,116)=.62; p=.54, n.s.) was assessed equally. In contrast, the participants showed different evaluation patterns for two of the data access options: allowing data access for *Family members* (F(2,117)=5.95 (HF);

$p < .01$) received higher agreements for household (M=4.86; SD=1.10) compared to social (M=4.69; SD=1.16) and intimate activities (M=4.56; SD=1.23); in accordance with that, data access for *Police and fire departments* (F(2,115)=8.79 (HF); $p < .01$) was also significantly higher related to household activities (M=4.49; SD=1.39) compared to social (M=4.15; SD=1.44) and intimate activities (M=4.08; SD=1.48).

Fig. 2. Data handling preferences for different activities (* = $p < .05$; ** = $p < .01$).

Related to the different **storage options**, neither *locally at my own home* (F(2,114)=.02; $p=.98$, n.s.) nor *stored in a cloud* (F(2,115)=1.96; $p=.15$, n.s.) received significantly different evaluations depending from the three activity types.

The results of the evaluated **storage duration** preferences depending on the three activity types are shown in Figure 3. Overall, the results of a two-way Friedman ANOVA analysis showed that the evaluation pattern of the storage duration was not equal for the three activities (F(2,120)=12.67; $p < .01$). Pairwise comparisons revealed effects between the three activity types, but not on a significant level. Nevertheless, looking at the descriptive results in Figure 3, it

Fig. 3. Storage Duration preferences for different activities.

can be seen that the evaluation patterns between household and social activities were rather similar. In contrast, intimate activities represented the only activity type for which the option *Data may not be stored at all* was chosen (9.90%, $n=12$).

Overall, the results regarding the three activity types showed a rather generic evaluation of VAAL technologies as only isolated differences between the three activity types were identified.

3.3 Relationships with Technology Perception and Acceptance (RQ3)

On the basis of the previous results, we conducted correlation analyses independent from the three activity types in order to identify relevant relationships between the preferences with regard to technical requirements and data handling on the one hand, and the perception and acceptance of VAAL technology on the other hand. The respective results are illustrated in Figure 4.

First of all, the results revealed a significant relationship between the perceived benefits and the acceptance of VAAL technologies ($\rho = .58$; $p < .01$) as well as between the perceived barriers and acceptance ($\rho = -.35$; $p < .01$). Beyond that, the technology requirements correlated with the perceived benefits ($\rho = .21$; $p < .05$) and the perceived barriers ($\rho = .33$; $p < .01$), but not directly with the acceptance of VAAL technologies. Data access showed a slight correlation with the perceived barriers ($\rho = -.18$; $p < .05$) and a stronger correlation with the perceived benefits ($\rho = .34$; $p < .01$) and even directly with the acceptance of VAAL technology ($\rho = .41$; $p < .01$). For the storage location, the results revealed relationships with the perceived benefits ($\rho = .28$; $p < .01$) and

Fig. 4. Data handling preferences related to technology acceptance.

the acceptance of VAAL technology ($\rho = .25$; $p < .05$). In contrast, the storage duration did neither correlate with the perceived benefits and barriers nor with the acceptance of VAAL technology. Among the preferences, technology requirements showed a correlation with the storage location ($\rho = .36$; $p < .01$). In addition, the storage location was related to data access ($\rho = .35$; $p < .01$) and the storage duration ($\rho = .27$; $p < .01$). Lastly, data access correlated also with storage duration ($\rho = .24$; $p < .01$).

In order to assess the relevance of the requirements and data handling preferences for the acceptance of VAAL technology, a linear (forward) regression analysis was conducted in the last step. The final regression model explained 48.4% (adj. $r^2 = .484$) of the variance of the acceptance of VAAL technology ($F(3,121) = 38.82$; $p < .01$) based on the constructs perceived benefits ($\beta = .51$; $p < .01$) and perceived barriers ($\beta = -.24$; $p < .01$) as well as data access ($\beta = .18$; $p < .05$). All other constructs (requirements, storage location, and storage duration) were excluded from analyses and did therefore not represent explaining predictors for the acceptance of VAAL technology.

4 Discussion

In this section, the results of the empirical study are discussed, starting with the key insights and answering the underlying research questions. Afterwards,

we derive implications for technology development and design, describe the limitations of the conducted approach, and highlight recommendations for future work in this research area.

4.1 Social implications of empirical findings

The present study investigated technology requirements and data handling preferences of potential future users of video-based AAL technology for three different activities of daily living. Therefore, study participants were introduced to safety-critical scenarios with a household activity, a social activity and an intimate activity respectively. For each activity, technology acceptance, several conditions of technology usage (e.g., on/off switching, controllability, video/audio recordings), data access, and data storage location and duration were assessed. The aim was to understand the least and most important aspects of technology requirements and data handling (RQ1), to examine the influence of activity type on the single evaluations (RQ2) and lastly, to investigate the relevance of these preferences for the acceptance of video-based AAL (RQ3).

Concerning the evaluation of the requirements, controlling and checking the technology and being able to switch it on and off resulted in the most important prerequisites. These findings are completely in line with literature assessing AAL in general (e.g., [37, 45, 46]). Previous studies report that older adults (i.e., AAL users) consider it as part of autonomy preservation wanting to control technology and deliberately switching devices on and off is one way of exercising this control [46, 37]. Furthermore, there was no clear trend for or against monitoring all activities, which underlines the importance of assessing requirements for single activity types to obtain valuable information. Indeed, monitoring all household activities is slightly accepted but not the recording of all social and intimate activities. This reflects current literature about camera monitoring, reporting more private rooms as less acceptable to be filmed [13, 49] and intimate activities as more critical and uncomfortable to be captured [39, 41, 47, 48]. Similarly, evaluations for audio and video recordings did not reveal any overall positioning. Clear patterns as well as significantly different positioning emerged when zooming into the specific activities. No video recordings were slightly favoured for intimate activity but not for social and household activity. Only audio recording was an acceptable option for intimate activity but not for social and household activity. Considering these nuanced findings across activities, the low acceptance rates for video-based monitoring in the own home documented in the literature [40, 49, 13] may mostly refer to the monitoring of these intimate moments and not towards the entire home.

Another important aspect for potential users of VAAL is the question of who accesses the data. In the evaluation of data access, a clear pattern could be observed that people with whom one can have a direct relationship and contact are more likely to be granted access. In contrast, health insurance and companies which are rather collective and anonymous identities with potential economical interests are strictly rejected. This rejection did not differ across the three activities and is in line with previous findings (e.g., [38, 50, 27]). Besides access

for oneself, medical personnel is the most accepted person group, who have an interest in one's health and well-being. The fact that health matters independently from activity, may be one reason why there is no significant difference for medical personnel among the activities assessed - health matters in any scenario equally. The willingness to share data with medical personnel is partly in line with [27, 50]. However, for family members, as well as police and fire departments the data access allowance was rated differently for the three activities. For the intimate activity scenario, data access was least granted whereas providing family members and police and fire corps access to data from the household activity was rather accepted. This result suggests differing privacy and intimacy implications for each activity being filmed which may explain these different evaluations among the scenarios. As already known from previous studies, the comfortableness and showing of skin are highly sensitive and monitoring is critical or rejected [39, 41]. Furthermore, the scenario of the household activity described a fire incident which may have further impacted the decision to let police and fire corps access the data. Independent from activity, local storage was strongly favoured whereas cloud/external storage was slightly rejected. This may be partly explained by the main concerns of VAAL which are fear of data hacking, data misuse and unauthorized data access [10, 11, 35]. Naturally, the more public the storage location, the less control over it and the higher the potential risk that these concerns become reality. In addition, the preference for local storage is in line with previous investigations [38]. Interestingly, regarding storage duration, participants did not decide with the same logic - the longer the data exists, the more possibilities of hacking and misusing it. Indeed, for household and social activity participants preferred relatively long storage of one year the most. If looking at the relative proportion of the most favoured storage duration of intimate activities the most selected one was unlimited storage. At first sight, this might seem very disruptive but when considering the remaining evaluations, a relatively short duration of one-week storage was the second most selected option and, different from the other two activities, some participants even selected no storage at all for the data from the intimate activity. The fact that the evaluation patterns for storage duration differed across activities is further evidence that technical preferences for VAAL usage are strongly dependent on what activity is monitored. The overall trend towards a rather long storage duration suggests that participants may have considered the informational value of past data to allow for a better understanding of their own health. Indeed, one of the benefits of lifelogging and continuous monitoring and data storage is that it enables the detection of abnormalities and deviations from normal behaviour and usual routines [4, 51].

Furthermore, as part of the third research question, relationships between technological requirements, data handling and technology acceptance together with benefits and barriers were looked at. As logical, benefits had a positive relationship with acceptance whereas barriers had a negative one, which just confirms them as concepts. Technological requirements affect perceptions of benefits and barriers but not directly the technology acceptance. It may be that several

technological requirements or the lacking thereof may even be perceived as either benefits or barriers respectively. Frequently framed under data handling, data access, storage location, and storage duration are all connected with each other. When looking at their relationships with VAAL acceptance and perceived benefits and barriers, storage duration seems to be irrelevant and storage location is only slightly relevant for perceived benefits and to a lesser extent for acceptance. In turn, data access was revealed to be the most relevant facet of data handling preferences impacting perceptions of benefits and barriers as well as acceptance. Linear regression analysis further confirmed data access as the only facet of data handling which serves as a predictor of acceptance of VAAL. This makes sense, considering that people strongly protect themselves from the disclosure of harmful and/or sensitive information about themselves to preserve privacy [34, 33] and protecting data is one of the most important factors for users of pervasive health-monitoring systems [45]. Related to the study result that among data handling only data access predicts acceptance, this means that disclosure happens of course through data access no matter where data is stored and how long it is stored there.

4.2 Managerial recommendations, limitations and future work

The insights of this study enable us to derive some recommendations and implications for future technology development and design in order to enable the consideration of users' needs and requirements.

Focusing on technical requirements, future users should be able to control the technology at any time (e.g., switching on/off) as it represents a central prerequisite for sustainable usage and adoption. Further, access to recorded data should be controlled by the users themselves. It is of utmost importance that data access for third parties, such as companies and health insurance, serves as a "No Go" and represents central obstacles to the acceptance and adoption of VAAL technologies in the everyday life. These recommendations are even more important in case the technology is aimed to be used to record potentially intimate activities and thus sensitive information. The differences in evaluations between the three activities highlight that there is not one customized technological solution. One single user may want to customize each area in his or her home differently or different activities detected should be visualized differently and access allowances should vary. These variances among one single (potential) user mean that the system and the single devices should account for that and make this detailed customization possible. Taking the storage options into account, local storage is preferred, however, storage options played a minor role in perceptions and acceptance of VAAL technology. Overall, it should be aimed at providing transparent and comprehensible information about functions, requirements, and data handling of using VAAL technology in order to enable a trustworthy and sustainable usage of VAAL technology.

Besides novel insights and derived implications, there are also limitations of this study that should be considered for future research enabling to derive some ideas for future work in the field.

Starting with sample-related aspects, the sample of our study was comparably small and not perfectly balanced regarding age, gender, and educational level. In particular, future studies should try to reach larger samples, including higher proportions of older people and people with lower educational levels. In addition, it has to be mentioned that the participants from this study originated from Germany and Bulgaria. Country- and culture-related comparisons were not part of this investigation, but should be focused on in future analyses. Beyond that, more detailed country- and culture-specific analyses would be useful to gain more insights into value- and culture-based differences in data handling preferences, technology acceptance, and perception.

The applied methodological approach was useful to investigate whether activity types affect the preferences of requirements and data handling. However, only three rather generic types of daily activities were considered disregarding specific activities, such as care-related aspects or severe health situations, e.g., falls or emergencies. Future studies should therefore also consider more specific activities and situations to investigate potential changes within the evaluation patterns of data handling and preferences. Beyond that, the conducted survey and analyses enabled only absolute evaluations of the technical requirements and data handling. For future research, it would be useful to analyze the relative importance of the different aspects (e.g., by applying conjoint analysis approaches). As a last idea for future research, future users' knowledge, information, and mental models can be decisive for the adoption of innovative technologies. Here, it would be interesting to analyze and investigate potential influences of the users' perceived and real knowledge about the specific technology and data handling on the evaluations of using VAAL technology in the everyday life.

5 Conclusion

The conducted quantitative study applied an online survey to identify potential users' most relevant requirements and data handling preferences for using VAAL technology. The results revealed a rather generic evaluation of VAAL (being only sporadically influenced by specific activity types) and identified data access to be a relevant predictor for technology acceptance in addition to technology-related perceived benefits and barriers. The insights are used to derive implications for user-centred technology development and design by considering user-relevant requirements and data handling preferences.

Acknowledgements

The authors thank all participants for sharing their opinions and needs in the context of privacy and acceptance of VAAL technologies. We also thank Ivanina Buchkova for her research support. This work resulted from the project Vi-suAAL "Privacy-Aware and Acceptable Video-Based Technologies and Services

for Active and Assisted Living” and was funded by the European Union’s Horizon 2020 research and innovation programme under the Marie Skłodowska-Curie grant agreement No 861091.

References

1. Rashidi, P., Mihailidis, A: A survey on ambient-assisted living tools for older adults. *IEEE J. Biomed. Health Inform.* **7**, 579–590 (2013)
2. Blackman, S., Matlo, C., Bobrovitskiy, C., Waldoch, A., Fang, M.L., Jackson, P., Mihailidis, A., Nygård, L., Astell, A., Sixsmith, A. Ambient assisted living technologies for aging well: A scoping review. *J. Intell. Sys.* **25**, 55–69 (2016)
3. Calvaresi, D., Cesarini, D., Sernani, P., Marinoni, M., Dragoni, A.F., Sturm, A. Exploring the ambient assisted living domain: A systematic review. *J. Ambient Intell. Hum. Comput.* **8**, 239–257 (2017)
4. Climent-Pérez, P., Spinsante, S., Mihailidis, A., Flórez-Revuelta, F. A review on video-based active and assisted living technologies for automated lifelogging. *Exp. Sys. Appl.* **139**, 112847 (2020)
5. Ćirić, I.T., Čojbašić, Ž; M., Ristić-Durrant, D.D., Nikolić, V.D., Ćirić, M.V., Simonović, M.B., Pavlović, I.R. Thermal vision based intelligent system for human detection and tracking in mobile robot control system. *Therm. Sci.* **20**, 1553–1559 (2016)
6. Chen, L., Yang, H., Liu, P. Intelligent robot arm: Vision-based dynamic measurement system for industrial applications. In: Yu, H., Liu, J., Liu, L., Ju, Z., Liu, Y., Zhou, D. (eds.) *Lecture Notes in Computer Science: Vol. 11744. Intelligent Robotics and Applications*, pp. 120–130. Springer, Berlin/Heidelberg (2019)
7. Sefat, M.S., Khan, A.A.M., Shahjahan, M. Implementation of vision based intelligent home automation and security system. In: *Proceedings of the International Conference on Informatics, Electronics & Vision (ICIEV)*, Dhaka, Bangladesh, pp. 1–6 (2014)
8. Mubashir, M., Shao, L., Seed, L. A survey on fall detection: Principles and approaches. *Neurocomputing*.**100**, 144–152 (2013)
9. Sathyanarayana, S., Satzoda, R.K., Sathyanarayana, S., Thambipillai, S. Vision-based patient monitoring: A comprehensive review of algorithms and technologies. *J. Ambient. Intell. Hum. Comput.* **9**, 225–251 (2018)
10. Peek, S.T., Wouters, E.J., Van Hoof, J., Luijkx, K.G., Boeije, H.R., Vrijhoef, H.J. Factors influencing acceptance of technology for aging in place: A systematic review. *Int. J. Med. Inform.* **83**, 235–248 (2014)
11. Lorenzen-Huber, L., Boutain, M., Camp, L.J., Shankar, K., Connelly, K.H. Privacy, technology, and aging: A proposed framework. *Ageing Int.* **36**, 232–252 (2011)
12. Jaschinski, C. Independent Aging with the Help of Smart Technology: Investigating the Acceptance of Ambient Assisted Living Technologies. Ph.D. Thesis, University of Twente, Twente (2018)
13. Himmel, S., Ziefle, M. Smart home medical technologies: Users’ requirements for conditional acceptance. *i-com.* **15**, 39–50 (2016)
14. Offermann-van Heek, J., Schomakers, E.M., Ziefle, M. Bare necessities? How the need for care modulates the acceptance of ambient assisted living technologies. *Int. J. Med. Inform.* **127**, 147–156 (2019)
15. Wang, L., Gu, T., Tao, X., Lu, J. Sensor-based human activity recognition in a multi-user scenario. In: Tscheligi, M. et al. (eds.) *AmI 2009. Lecture Notes in Computer Science (Vol. 5859)*, pp. 78–87. Springer, Berlin/Heidelberg (2009)

16. Schoeppe, S., Alley, S., Van Lippevelde, W., Bray, N.A., Williams, S.L., Duncan, M.J., Vandelanotte, C. Efficacy of interventions that use apps to improve diet, physical activity and sedentary behaviour: A systematic review. *Int. J. Behav. Nut. Phys. Act.* **13**, 127 (2016)
17. Nambu, M., Nakajima, K., Noshiro, M., Tamura, T. An algorithm for the automatic detection of health conditions. *IEEE Engin. Med. Bio. Mag.* **24**, 38–42 (2005)
18. Meditskos, G., Plans, P.M., Stavropoulos, T.G., Benois-Pineau, J., Buso, V., Kompatsiaris, I. Multi-modal activity recognition from egocentric vision, semantic enrichment and lifelogging applications for the care of dementia. *J. Vis. Comm. Image Repres.* **51**, 169–190 (2018)
19. Shi, G., Chan, C.S., Li, W.J., Leung, K.-S., Zou, Y., Jin, Y. Mobile human airbag system for fall protection using mems sensors and embedded svm classifier. *IEEE Sens. J.* **9**, 495–503 (2008)
20. Postawka, A., Rudy, J. Lifelogging system based on averaged Hidden Markov Models: Dangerous activities recognition for caregiver support. *Comput. Sci.* **19**, 257–278 (2018)
21. Jalal, A., Kamal, S., Kim, D. A depth video sensor-based lifelogging human activity recognition system for elderly care in smart indoor environments. *Sensors.* **14**, 11735–11759 (2014)
22. Davis F.D. Perceived usefulness, perceived ease of use, and user acceptance of information technology. *MIS Q.* **13** 319–340 (1989)
23. Venkatesh, V., Morris, M.G., Davis, G.B., Davis, F.D. User acceptance of information technology: Toward a unified view. *MIS Q.* **27**, 425–478 (2003)
24. Rahimi, B., Nadri, H., Afshar, H. L., Timpka, T. A systematic review of the technology acceptance model in health informatics. *Appl. Clin. Inform.* **9** (3), 604–634 (2018)
25. Jaschinski, C., Ben Allouch, S. Why Should I Use This? Identifying Incentives for Using AAL Technologies. In: De Ruyter, B., Kameas, A., Chatzimisios, P., Mavrommati, I. (eds.). *Ambient Intelligence, Lecture Notes in Computer Science (LNCS)*, Volume 9425, pp. 155–170. Springer, Cham, Switzerland (2015)
26. Wilkowska, W. *Acceptance of eHealth Technology in Home Environments: Advanced Studies on User Diversity in Ambient Assisted Living*. Apprimus Verlag, Aachen, Germany (2015)
27. Wilkowska, W., Offermann-van Heek, J., Florez-Revuelta, F., Ziefle, M. Video cameras for lifelogging at home: Preferred visualization modes, acceptance, and privacy perceptions among German and Turkish participants. *Int. J. Hum.–Comput. Inter.* **37**, 1436–1454 (2021).
28. Westin, A.F. *Privacy and Freedom*. Atheneum, New York, NY, USA (1967)
29. Marshall, N.J. Dimensions of Privacy Preferences. *Multivar. Behav. Res.* **9**, 255–271 (1974)
30. Burgoon, J.K. Privacy and communication. *Ann. Int. Commun. Assoc.* **6**, 206–249 (1982)
31. Altman, I. *Privacy: A Conceptual Analysis*. In: Carson, D.H. (ed.) *Man-Environment Interactions: Evaluations and Applications: Part 2. Environmental Design Research Association: Washington, DC, USA*, pp. 3–28 (1974)
32. Nissenbaum, H. *Privacy in Context*. Stanford University Press: Stanford, CA, USA (2009)
33. Lombardi, D.B., Ciceri, M.R. More than defense in daily experience of privacy: The functions of privacy in digital and physical environments. *Eur. J. Psychol.* **12**, 115–136 (2016)

34. Pedersen, D. M. Psychological functions of privacy. *Journal of environmental psychology*, 17(2), 147-156 (1997)
35. Demiris, G., Rantz, M.J., Aud, M.A., Marek, K.D., Tyrer, H.W., Skubic, M., Hussam, A.A. Older adults' attitudes towards and perceptions of 'smart home' technologies: A pilot study. *Med. Inform. Internet Med.* **29**, 87-94 (2004)
36. Lapiere N.; Meunier J.; Arnaud A. S.; Filiatrault J.; Paquin, M.-H.; Duclos, C.; Dumoulin C.; Rousseau, J. Older women's perceptions of a programmable video monitoring system at home: A pilot study. *Gerontechnology*. **4(17)**, 245-254 (2018)
37. Maidhof, C.; Ziefle, M.; Offermann, J. Exploring Privacy: Mental Models of Potential Users of AAL Technology. In *ICT4AWE 2022 - Proceedings of the 8th International Conference on Information and Communication Technologies for Ageing Well and e-Health (2022)*
38. Wilkowska, W., Offermann-van Heek, J., Colonna, L., Ziefle, M. (2020). Two faces of privacy: Legal and human-centered perspectives of lifelogging applications in home environments. In *Human Aspects of IT for the Aged Population. Healthy and Active Aging: 6th International Conference, ITAP 2020, Copenhagen, Denmark, July 19-24*, Springer, pp. 545-564 (2020)
39. Caine, K., Šabanovic, S., Carter, M. The effect of monitoring by cameras and robots on the privacy enhancing behaviors of older adults. In: *Proceedings of the Seventh Annual ACM/IEEE International Conference on Human-Robot Interaction*, Boston, MA, USA, pp. 343-350 (2012).
40. Arning, K., Ziefle, M. "Get that camera out of my house!" conjoint measurement of preferences for video-based healthcare monitoring systems in private and public places. In: *Lecture Notes in Computer Science (Including Subseries Lecture Notes in Artificial Intelligence and Lecture Notes in Bioinformatics)*. Springer, Cham, Switzerland, pp. 152-164 (2015)
41. Maidhof, C., Hashemifard, K., Offermann, J., Ziefle, M., Florez-Revuelta, F. Underneath Your Clothes: A Social and Technological Perspective on Nudity in The Context of AAL Technology. In *Proceedings of the 15th International Conference on PErvasive Technologies Related to Assistive Environments*, Crete, Greece, July 2022, pp. 439-445 (2022)
42. Londei, S.T., Rousseau, J., Ducharme, F., St-Arnaud, A., Meunier, J., Saint-Arnaud, J., Giroux, F. An intelligent videomonitoring system for fall detection at home: Perceptions of elderly people. *J. Telemed. Telecare*. **15**, 383-390 (2009)
43. Offermann-van Heek, J., Ziefle, M. Nothing else matters! Trade-offs between perceived benefits and barriers of AAL technology usage. *Front. Public Health*. **7**, 134 (2019)
44. Beach, S., Schulz, R., Downs, J., Matthews, J., Barron, B., Seelman, K. Disability, age, and informational privacy attitudes in quality of life technology applications: Results from a national web survey. *ACM Trans. Access. Comput.* **2**, 1-21 (2009)
45. McNeill, A., Briggs, P., Pywell, J., Coventry, L. Functional privacy concerns of older adults about pervasive health-monitoring systems. In *Proceedings of the 10th international conference on pervasive technologies related to assistive environments*, pp. 96-102 (2017)
46. Berridge, C., Zhou, Y., Lazar, A., Porwal, A., Mattek, N., Gothard, S., Kaye, J. Control Matters in Elder Care Technology: Evidence and Direction for Designing It In. In *Designing Interactive Systems Conference*, pp. 1831-1848 (2022)
47. Choe, E. K., Consolvo, S., Jung, J., Harrison, B., Kientz, J. A. Living in a glass house: a survey of private moments in the home. In *Proceedings of the 13th international conference on Ubiquitous computing*, Springer, pp. 41-44 (2011)

48. Offermann, J., Wilkowska, W., Maidhof, C., Ziefle, M. Shapes of You? Investigating the Acceptance of Video-Based AAL Technologies Applying Different Visualization Modes. *Sensors*, **23(3)**, 1143 (2023)
49. Ziefle, M., Himmel, S., Wilkowska, W. When Your Living Space Knows What You Do: Acceptance of Medical Home Monitoring by Different Technologies. In: *Information Quality in e-Health.*, Holzinger, A., Simonik, KM. (eds). Springer Berlin Heidelberg, pp. 607–624 (2011)
50. Boise, L., Wild, K., Mattek, N., Ruhl, M., Dodge, H. H., Kaye, J. Willingness of older adults to share data and privacy concerns after exposure to unobtrusive in-home monitoring. *Gerontechnology: international journal on the fundamental aspects of technology to serve the ageing society*, **11(3)**, 428 (2013)
51. Selke, S. (Ed.). *Lifelogging: Digital self-tracking and Lifelogging-between disruptive technology and cultural transformation.* Springer (2016)